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Effect of Problem-Based Learning on Students Academic Performance and Retention in Senior Secondary Schools Biology in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined effect of Problem-Based Learning Strategy on students' academic performance and retention in Biology in Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Quasi experimental research of pre-test, post-test, control design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 10,540 senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. 120 senior secondary school year 2 (SS 2), (comprised 30 male and 30 female for the experimental group, and 30 male and 30 female for the control group) were sampled using multistage sampling technique. Biology Performance Test (BPT) and Biology Retention Test (BRT) were developed by the researcher and used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts, all from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, Kuda-Richardson-21 (KR-21) was used and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 and 0.81 were obtained for both BPT and BRT. Four objectives, four research questions and four hypotheses guided the study. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study revealed that Problem-Based learning have higher effect on the academic performance and retention of students in Biology. There was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students. Thus the study recommends that teachers should be encouraged to incorporate Problem-Based Learning strategy into their teaching /learning activities.

Keywords: Problem-based learning, students academic performance, learning retention

INTRODUCTION

A lot of changes have taken place in Nigerian education system over the years as educational planners and subject teachers have tried, sometimes with doubtful success, to keep pace with the galloping dynamism in the contemporary world of science, technology, and information. In Nigeria, the National Policy on Education stipulates that secondary school education should equip students to live effectively in modern age of science and technology (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). The proper teaching and handling of science and technology subjects in schools by qualified hands will result in the training of the minds of students in the understanding of the world around them in the acquisition of appropriate skills, capacities, and competencies necessary for them to live and contribute to the development of their

society. In pursuance of this, several governments have planned that, scientific and technical subjects should be taught in such a way as to ensure that every secondary school student has access to science and technology irrespective of gender and creed.

In Nigeria for example, as a follow up of the Adebo Commission, the 6-3-3-4 system of education was put in place in 1983. The 3-year junior secondary school education was centred on pre-vocational subjects while the 3-year senior secondary catered for sciences and vocational subjects. According to Oyedeki, (2002) Nigeria as a nation has taken some shots at education reforms since the return of the Country to the democratically elected government in 1999, to fight the deterioration in the education system which has spanned a long period of time, but became more pronounced within the last decade. There is no single method which can be regarded as best for every teaching situation. There are a number of criteria available that may guide the teacher in the choice of any given method of teaching which include: the content to be taught, objectives to be achieved, time available, the number of students, teachers' preferences and individual differences, the type of lesson, facilities available, needs and interest of the class, among others (Omeodu, 2022, & Mtsem, 2011). It has also been reported by Munawaroh (2017) that teaching method affects the responses of students and determines whether they are interested, motivated and involved in a lesson in such way as to engage in a good learning.

Ogunniyi (2009) asserted that one of the most persistent and compelling problems besetting academic achievement in Nigeria is the poor quality of teaching. This fall in standard of performance at post primary level is incontrovertibly attributable to pedagogical approaches adopted by teachers in schools. It has been reported that learning and understanding of school subjects have been frustrated by the clumsy methods and instructional materials used (Etukudo & Utin, 2006). To support this assertion, Salau in Emaikwu (2012), submitted that many researchers have adduced that poor performance in public examination is traceable to teaching techniques by teachers. The resultant effect is the low achievement and low retention level in students' outcome both in internal and external examinations. Sequel to this, there is a wide spread concern among parents and public about the methods used in teaching at the secondary school level especially computer science in Nigeria.

The method employed by the teachers to impart knowledge on the learners is referred to as methodology. Teaching method is a strategy or plan that outlines the approach that teachers intend to take in order to achieve the desirable learning objectives. It involves the ways teachers organize and use techniques of subject matter, teaching tools and teaching materials to meet teaching objectives. Akinfe, Olofinniyi and Fashiku (2012) noted that most untrained teachers point accusing fingers at students rather than on themselves when the students are unable to carry out the expected behaviour at the end of the lesson or examinations. Therefore, teachers' plan should include: Choice of appropriate teaching method, Choice of appropriate teaching materials, Intensive research on the topic to be taught and determination of the objectives for the lesson. Some of the teaching methods used in the teaching of science include lecture method, laboratory method, problem based learning, flipped classroom, science quiz, guided discovery method, field trip method among others. Specifically, the use of problem based learning as a method for teaching Biology in secondary schools is new to many teachers who are yet to clarify how to use it and effective and suitable it is in the classroom.

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is a teaching method in which complex real-world problems are used as the vehicle to promote student learning of concepts and principles as opposed to direct presentation of facts and concepts. In addition to course content, PBL can promote the development of critical thinking skills, problem-solving abilities, and communication skills. It can also provide opportunities for working in groups, finding and evaluating research materials, and life-long learning (Allen, Duch & Grosh, 2001 in Aji & Khan, 2019).

Problem based Learning can be incorporated into any learning situation. This approach can be used over the entire semester as the primary method of teaching. Problem Based Learning can also be used to create assessment items. One of the main connecting point of PBL is the fact that it is applicable in real-world problem and any subject area can be adapted to PBL with a little creativity. While the core problems will

vary among disciplines, there are some characteristics of good PBL problems that transcend fields includes the following:

- i. The problem must motivate students to seek out a deeper understanding of concepts.
- ii. The problem should require students to make reasonable decisions and to defend them.
- iii. The problem should incorporate the content objectives in such a way as to connect it to previous courses/knowledge.
- iv. If used for a group project, the problem needs a level of complexity to ensure that the students must work together to solve it.
- v. If used for a multistage project, the initial steps of the problem should be open-ended and engaging to draw students into the problem.

The rationale for science teaching shifted as discovery strategy was adopted worldwide, this was because students memorize facts and concepts, most of which they did not understand. Consequently, memorization resulted in lack of application of concepts to solving daily problems. There was also a great burst of interest as the guided discovery strategy was adopted in the Nigeria Curriculum (Akpomudjere, 2020). The author also believed that learning is known to take place not only through observation alone but also through organization, structuring and reconstructing of concepts. This idea contradicts the teaching techniques of Problem based learning, where concepts are not essentially structured and organized in an interrelated complex. But Problem Based learning makes students to research into facts and know how and why thing are the way they are.

At the same time, many researchers have been able to prove that one of the best means of teaching science is through concept mapping strategy which is relatively new in Nigeria and a number of teachers both professionals and non-professionals were yet to be at home with the strategy.

It is against this background that Adebule and Aborishade (2014) recommend several measures, with the aim to improve students' attitude and achievement at the secondary school level. Amongst the measures recommended are the appropriate use of teaching methods, instructional media and other instructional designs (Akpomudjere, 2020). The use of Problem-Based Learning as a method suitable for teaching biology in Secondary school was a welcome development. Thus the need to determine its effectiveness in respect of students' academic performance and retention in other to guarantee its usage especially for the teaching of biology.

Statement of the Problem

An important aspect of Biology such as digestive system that cannot be overlooked has been reported to be difficult for students to learn. This is very evident in the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's Report (2018) which reported that students performed very poorly in drawing and identification of the digestive system of an organism. Similarly, the National Examination Council (2014) Chief Examiners Report showed that students have difficulty in arranging responses in questions pertaining to digestion. The problem of poor academic performance and retention of students in biology have posed a great concern to Biology Educators and relevant stake-holders in education. Many researchers partly attributed the cause of students' poor performance to wrong method of teaching used by the teachers, or students' styles of learning. The question is what method of teaching could be better, if adopted, for students to achieve better performance in external examinations? Would the introduction of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) increase students' academic performance and retention? The need to find answers to this question provides the rationale for exploring the 'effect of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) on students' academic performance and retention in Biology in SSS in Port-Harcourt Metropolis'.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this research was to ascertain the effect of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) on Senior Secondary School (SSS) students' academic performance and retention in Biology, specifically focusing on the digestive system of birds, in Port-Harcourt Metropolis. In specific terms, the study sought to;

1. Determine the difference in the academic performance of students taught Digestive system using PBL and Demonstration teaching method.

2. Examine the difference in the retention of students taught Digestive system using PBL and Demonstration teaching method.
3. Investigate the difference in academic performance of male and female students taught Digestive system using PBL.
4. Ascertain the difference in the retention of male students taught Digestive system using PBL.

Research Questions

The study was guided by four research questions: They are as follows:

1. What is the difference in the mean scores of students taught Digestive system using PBL and those taught with Demonstration teaching method?
2. What is the difference in the mean retention score of students taught Digestive system using PBL and those taught with Demonstration teaching method?
3. What is the difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught Digestive system using PBL?
4. What is the difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Digestive system using PBL?

Hypotheses

Four null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught Digestive system using PBL and those taught with Demonstration teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught Digestive system using PBL and those taught with Demonstration teaching method.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female students taught Digestive system using PBL.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of male and female students taught Digestive system using PBL.

Method and Materials.

The design of the study is a pretest, posttest quasi-experimental and control group design. The diagram for the design is shown below;

Where

- | | | |
|------------------|---|----------------------------------|
| E | - | Stands for experimental groups |
| C | - | Control group |
| X | - | Treatment |
| Q ₁ | - | Pre-test for experimental |
| Q ₂ | - | Post-test for experimental |
| Q ₃ | - | Pretest for control group |
| Q ₄ | - | Post-test for control group |
| Q ₅ - | | Retention for experimental group |
| Q ₆ - | | Retention for control group |

The study was carried out in Port-Harcourt Metropolis comprising Obio/Akpor and Port-Harcourt Local Government Areas. The population of the study comprised of 10540 students of in the 43 public senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor and Port-Harcourt Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

The sample for study was 120 SS2 biology students, 60 students in experimental and 60 in control groups. In the experimental group there were 30 male and 30 female students, while in the control group there were also 30 male and 30 female students.. Multistage sampling technique was used in the study. The first stage was a purposive sampling technique used to select two schools - one from PHALGA and the other

from OBALGA, based on convenience. In each school, one intact class was randomly selected. Again, one school was randomly chosen as experimental and the other was control group. The SS2 class was purposely selected because it is a more stable class, since Biology is just introduced in SS1 and SS3 being examination class.

Table 3.1: Sample Distribution

Groups	Male	Female	Total
Experimental	30	30	60
Control	30	30	60
Total	60	60	120

The instruments developed by the researcher for this study were Biology Performance Test (BPT) and Biology Retention Test (BRT). The BPT and BRT were cognitive test which contained 30 items of multiple-choice item questions; option A- D which was used to test students' knowledge in digestive system of Bird. The instruments consisted of two parts, Part A was designed to elicit personal information from the respondents while Part B was a 30-items of BAT with options A to D, and only one correct option was key, and the others were distractor. Each right answer was scored two (2) marks and zero mark for wrong answer. BRT was reshuffled version of BPT.

The instruments were validated by three lecturers in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Curriculum and Instruction and Department of Science Education (Biology), all from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The corrections and recommendations were effected in the final copy of the instrument.

In order to test reliability of the instrument, the research instrument (BPT and BRT) were distributed to 30 senior secondary students in Kalabari National College, Asari-Toru Local government Area, Rivers State. The selected students were not part of those engaged in the study. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, Kuda-Richardson-21 (KR-21) method was used and a reliability coefficient obtained were 0.78 and 0.81. Therefore, the instruments were considered to be reliable for this study.

The researcher visited the various schools with an introductory letter from the Head of Department (HOD) and obtained permission from the school authorities. The researcher also discussed the study plan with biology teachers in the selected schools who served as research assistants. The study was done for a period of three weeks during which the topics were covered. A pretest of BPT was administered, before treatment, in the first week of the research to the experimental group and the control group all in an intact class. In the second week of the research, the lesson was taught to the two groups; where the experimental group was taught using PBL, the control group was taught with the Demonstration teaching method. After the lessons, BPT was re-shuffled and administered as post-test. To obtain the retention scores of students, the test was re-administered to students after three weeks. After the responses were obtained, the various scores were collated for analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the main and interaction effects of categorical variables on a continuous variable which co-vary with the dependent variable. The control variables are called the covariates. It is used in experimental studies when researchers want to remove the effects of some antecedent variables. For example, Pretest scores are used as covariates in pretest and post-test experimental design.

RESULTS PRESENTATION

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the academic performance of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method?*

Table 4.1: Mean Difference in the Academic Performance of Students Taught Biology Using Problem Based Learning and Demonstration Method

Groups	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean difference	Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Control	60	15.67	4.65	25.65	8.95	9.98	8.76
Experimental	60	16.13	5.24	34.87	7.05	18.74	
TOTAL	120						

Field Data, 2024

Table 4.1 shows the mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of students taught biology using problem based learning (experimental) and demonstration method (control group). The experimental group has a pretest mean score of 16.13 and standard deviation of 5.24 and a post-test mean value of 34.87 and a standard deviation of 7.05 while the control group has a pre-test mean value of 15.67 and a standard deviation of 4.65 and a post-test mean value of 25.65 and a standard deviation of 7.05. The mean gain in their achievement was 8.76 in favour of the experimental group. The result of the analysis revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. This implies that the experimental group has a higher performance mean score than that of the control group. Since the experimental group had a higher mean performance score, it simply implies that the use of Problem Based learning had a higher effect on the academic performance of Biology students.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference in the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method?*

Table 4.2: Mean Difference in the Retention of Students Taught Biology Using Problem Based Learning and Demonstration Method

Groups	N	Post-test		Retention		Mean Diff.	Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Control	60	25.65	8.95	21.43	5.46	4.22	1.52
Experimental	60	34.84	7.05	29.10	5.28	5.74	
TOTAL	120						

Field Data, 2024

Table 4.2 displayed the mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test retention scores of experimental group and control group: In post-test, experimental group had a mean score of 34.84 and standard deviation of 7.05 and a retention scores mean value of 29.10 and a standard deviation of 5.28 while the control group has a post-test mean value of 25.65 and a standard deviation of 8.95 and a retention mean value of 21.43 and a standard deviation of 5.46. The result of the analysis revealed that the experimental group had a better retention rate than the control group. This implies that the experimental group had a higher retention mean score than that of the control group. Since the experimental group had a higher mean retention score, it simply implies that the use of Problem Based learning had a higher effect on the retention of students in Biology.

Research Question 3: *What is the difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning and demonstration method?*

Table 4.3: Difference in the Academic Performance of Male and Female Students taught Biology using Problem-Based Learning

Gender	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean diff.	Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	30	17.00	5.50	25.06	6.70	18.06	1.34
Female	30	15.27	4.91	24.67	7.48	19.4	
TOTAL	60						

Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.3 shows the mean and standard deviation of scores of both male and female students performance taught biology using Problem Based Learning. The result revealed that the Male students had a pre-test mean performance score of 17.00 and a standard deviation of 5.50 while the female students had a pretest mean value of 15.27 and a standard deviation of 4.91. The post mean score of male students was 25.06 and for females was 24.67. The mean gain in the achievement scores was 1.34 in favour of the male students. From the results displayed, it revealed a slight higher mean performance scores in favor of the Male students. Therefore, male students performed better than the female counterpart when taught with Problem Based Learning technique.

Research Question 4: *What is the difference in the retention score of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning?*

Table 4: Difference in the Retention Score of Male and Female Students Taught Biology Using Problem-Based Learning

Gender	N	Post-test		Retention		Mean Diff.	Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	30	25.06	6.70	24.53	4.97	5.53	0.47
Female	30	24.67	7.48	23.67	5.62	6.00	
TOTAL	60						

Table 4.4 shows the mean and standard deviation of scores in retention test of both male and female students taught using problem based learning. The result revealed that the Male students had a posttest mean score of 25.06 and a standard deviation of 6.70, while the female students had posttest mean score of 24.67 and standard deviation of 7.48. While for retention test; the Male students had a mean value of 24.53 and a standard deviation of 4.97, female had mean and standard deviation of 23.67 and 5.62. The mean gain was 0.47 in favour of the female students. Hence, female students' retention rate was slightly higher than the females.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method.

Table 4.5: ANCOVA analysis on academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and Demonstration method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	4279.340 ^a	2	2139.670	40.745	.000	Rejected
Intercept	3605.875	1	3605.875	68.665	.000	
Pretest	1514.540	1	1514.540	28.841	.000	
Groups	2568.044	1	2568.044	48.902	.000	
Error	6144.127	117	52.514			
Total	118904.000	120				
Corrected Total	10423.467	119				

a. R Squared = .411 (Adjusted R Squared = .400)

Table 4.7 shows the ANCOVA analysis of the academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method. From the result in the presented table, it was revealed that the p-value obtained was 0.000 which is less than the level of significance of 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected. That is there is a significant difference between the academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method

Table 4.6: ANCOVA analysis on the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	3013.161 ^a	2	1506.580	81.822	.000	Rejected
Intercept	1362.281	1	1362.281	73.985	.000	
Post	1249.827	1	1249.827	67.878	.000	
Group	316.381	1	316.381	17.183	.000	
Error	2154.306	117	18.413			
Total	81776.000	120				
Corrected Total	5167.467	119				

a. R Squared = .583 (Adjusted R Squared = .576)

Table 4.8 displays ANCOVA analysis on the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method. Analysis showed that the p-value obtained (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that the tested null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning.

Table 4.7: ANCOVA Analysis on the Academic Performance of Male and Female Students Taught Biology Using Problem-Based Learning.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	707.353 ^a	2	353.676	9.066	.000	
Intercept	3193.301	1	3193.301	81.858	.000	
Pretest	704.953	1	704.953	18.071	.000	Accepted
Group	8.392	1	8.392	.215	.645	
Error	2223.580	57	39.010			
Total	75872.000	60				
Corrected Total	2930.933	59				

a. R Squared = .241 (Adjusted R Squared = .215)

Table 4.9 reveals the ANCOVA analysis on the academic performance of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning. Because the p-value obtained was 0.645 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was adjudged to be accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning and demonstration teaching methods.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught biology using Problem Based Learning

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	666.846 ^a	2	333.423	19.461	.000	
Intercept	367.874	1	367.874	21.472	.000	Accepted
Posttest	655.580	1	655.580	38.265	.000	
Group	6.878	1	6.878	.401	.529	
Error	976.554	57	17.133			
Total	52452.000	60				
Corrected Total	1643.400	59				

a. R Squared = .406 (Adjusted R Squared = .385)

Table 4.10 reveals the ANCOVA analysis on the academic achievement of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning. Because the p-value obtained was 0.529 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was adjudged to be accepted. This implies that there is no significant differences in the retention of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study were discussed in line with the research questions and hypotheses in the study as follows;

Firstly, the findings revealed that the Problem Based Learning had a higher effect on the academic performance of students in Biology. The result of the analysis revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. The hypothesis conducted on the research question 1 showed that there is significant difference in the academic performance of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method. These findings are in agreement with the findings of Celik, Onder and Silay (2011) whose study investigated the effect of problem- based learning on students' success in Physics course and determined a significant difference between the control and experimental group in favour of problem based approach. The study is equally in agreement

with Nadya, Putu and Wayan (2018) who examine the effectiveness of problem-based learning toward biology learning outcomes in the programme of Basic Nursing Sciences and the results confirmed that problem based model is more effective to demonstration method.

Secondly, the finding revealed the effect of Problem Based Learning (PBL) on the retention of the students taught Biology. It was found that experimental group had a higher retention mean score than that of the control group. This implies that the use of Problem Based learning had a positive effect on the retention of students in Biology. Likewise, the hypothesis showed that there is a significant difference in the retention of senior secondary school students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration method. These findings are in line with the findings of Mine and Yusuf (2013), Sukran, Asiye and Suleyman (2015), who revealed that instructional strategy, employing creative teaching manipulatively increase academic performance of students. This study is opposed to the findings of Stephen and Schusslev (2013), whose work revealed that instructional model was not more important as other factors in driving students' interest and attitudes, and that grades and teachers' attitudes played a great role in determining students' interest and attitudes than instructional strategy.

Thirdly, the finding shows significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning. The overall difference in the performance scores was 1.34 in favour of the male students. Male students performed better than the female counterpart when taught with Problem Based Learning technique, though when tested the hypothesis was accepted, meaning that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female judging from the use of Problem-Based Learning in teaching Biology education. This study concurred with the study of Akinwumi and Falemu (2017) who investigated effect of problem-solving teaching approach on students' academic performance and determined that no significant difference exist between male and female students in the experimental group. However, this findings opposed the findings of; Altermatt and Kim, (2004) that revealed that boys perform better than girls in sciences because boys were exposed to hormones in the womb that lead to more analytical thinking in the brain and increased spatial abilities.

Moreover, the study also found the difference in the retention of male and female students taught biology using Problem Based Learning. The overall mean difference was 0.47 in favour of the female students. Hence, female students' retention rate was slightly higher than the males. However, the study established that there is no significant differences in the retention of male and female students taught biology using problem-based learning. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Hindu (2003) who also indicated that the retention of male and female students are insignificantly different for each other when taught Biology with student centered teaching approach.

Summary of the Study

This study investigated effect of Problem based learning on students' academic performance in senior secondary schools Biology in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. The objectives of the study were to determine the difference in the academic performance, retention of students taught biology using problem based learning and demonstration methods with regards to their gender. From these objectives, four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated. The study covered the academic performance and retention as well as gender of SS 2 students in Biology in public secondary schools using Problem Based Learning and demonstration method. The population was 10,540 students in all the Secondary School in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. multistage sampling was used to select sample size for the study which was 120 (30 male and 30 females for the experimental group and 30 male and 30 female for the control group) SS2 biology students from senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State were used. Biology Performance Test (BPT) was used to collect data before and after treatment was carried out on the research subjects. Face and content validity was carried out by experts, and a reliability test was carried out on the instrument using Kuda-Richardson (KR-21) a reliability coefficient obtained was 0.78. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Also the null hypotheses were tested with ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that students performed better in Problem Based Learning in Biology than those taught with the demonstration method of teaching. The findings also revealed that students' retention and performance

were high using Problem Based Learning than those taught with demonstration teaching classrooms. Also, there was no significant difference in the retention of male and female students taught Biology using Problem Based Learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discoveries of the finding, the following recommendations were made to the following categories:

1. STEM teachers' should be motivated to incorporate Problem Based Learning strategy into their learning, especially sciences; this will help to improve their performance and retention in their subject areas. This will also improve students' manipulative skill which encourages motor skills activities and therefore helping students retained knowledge for a long time without much revision.
2. Problem based learning strategic activities are fun, encourages group learning activities, it uses all the senses for it activities and boost the interest of students. Therefore, Problem Based Learning should be employed by teachers of Biology for students with learning disabilities such as dyscalculia, negative attitude or interest toward concept learning, inability to comprehend abstract concepts, etc.
3. Curriculum Planners should recommend the use of Problem Based Learning in Biology curriculum. This will enhance the application of the method by teachers and improve students' performance.
4. The government should encourage Biology teachers by sending them to workshops to learn how to use Problem Based Learning effectively in the classrooms. Also, opportunities such as scholarship or allowances should be given to teachers that had contributed on these areas in order to motivate teachers.

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